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Remarking An Analisation

Study of Character Human Strengths and Cognitive Impairment in Relation to Activity Status and Gender of Aged People

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**Suramya
Srivastava**
Research Scholar
Department Of Psychology
Deen Dayal Upadhyay
Gorakhpur University
Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Dhananjay Kumar
Professor
Department Of Psychology
Deen Dayal Upadhyay
Gorakhpur University
Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

The present study aimed to study the effect of activity status and gender on character human strengths and cognitive impairment. It also aimed to explore the relationship between character human strengths and cognitive impairment among aged people. Sample consisted of 100 individuals (51 male and 49 females), age ranged between 60-83 years. All the participants belonged to North-Eastern Uttar Pradesh, living with their families. Purposive Sampling was utilized for the selection of sample. Character human strengths was measured using VIA 72 and mild cognitive impairment (MCI) was measured using two measures namely, Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Hindi) (H-MoCA) and Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination (ACE III). The findings suggest that practicing professionals are more virtuous and have lower cognitive impairment than those who belong to retired and active and retired and inactive group. Further, the retired and inactive group and the females are more vulnerable to cognitive impairment. Moreover, character human strengths was correlated with cognitive impairment. The attained knowledge has counseling implications. There is a need to encourage aged individuals to cultivate character strengths through structured programs, community engagement, and cognitive training to support cognitive health. Additionally, promoting regular physical and intellectual activities through public health initiatives and social programs would help delay cognitive decline and enhance character human strengths. Policymakers should design initiatives that facilitate lifelong learning, social participation, physical fitness, and mental well-being among aged individuals in order to delay cognitive impairment.

Keywords Character Human Strengths (CHS), Cognitive Impairment, Activity Status, Aged People.

Introduction

Peterson and Seligman (2004) developed a system of classification of *character human strengths*, in which *virtues* refer to the core characteristics valued by moral philosophers and thinkers across ages while *strengths* refer to the psychological ingredients (psychological processes and mechanisms) that serve as distinct routes of manifesting specific virtues (Tripathi et al., 2015). The 6 virtues comprise of 24 strengths which are identified as cognitive strengths, emotional strengths, social and community strengths, protective strengths and transcendental strengths (Waterworth et al., 2019). These strengths are positive personality traits that reflect personal identity which produce positive outcomes and contribute to the greater collective good (Niemi, 2018).

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Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) refers to “confusion or memory loss that is happening more often or is getting worse during the past 12 months.” A few commons signs of Cognitive Impairment include the following: Memory loss, frequently asking the same question or repeating the same story over and over again, not recognizing familiar people and places, having trouble exercising, judgment, such as knowing what to do in an emergency, changes in mood or behavior, vision problems, following a recipe, difficulty planning and carrying out tasks or keeping track of monthly bills. Cognitive impairment can be in different domains or aspects of a person's cognitive function including memory, attention span, planning, reasoning, decision-making, language (comprehension, writing, and speech), executive functioning, and visuo-spatial functioning. (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Cognitive Impairment: A call for action, Now ! 2011)

Activity refers to a situation in which there is a lot of movement and action usually done regularly or for enjoyment. Here, activity status is categorized into three levels, namely practicing professionals, retired and active and finally retired and inactive. Practicing professionals are those who are aged but still working as a professional in their regular official settings. Retired and active group of individuals are those who are retired from their official settings or the home-makers who are leading an active life engaging themselves in household activities and recreational activities. The retired and inactive group of individuals is those who are aged and leading a sedentary life.

Objective of study

An exhaustive review of literature reveals that there is limited research related to the relationship of gender and activity status with character human strengths among elderly population (age range 60 to 80 years). Currently, there is a lack of studies directly examining the relationship of character strengths and virtues with cognitive impairment among the elderly population. In the light of these issues, the present work aimed to investigate the effect of activity status and gender on character human strengths and cognitive impairment. Further, the study also aimed to explore the strength and direction of the relationship between character human strengths and cognitive impairment among aged people. The specific objectives of the study were:

1. To study the effect of activity status on character human strengths.
2. To investigate the effect of activity status on cognitive impairment (using both measures Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Hindi) (H-MoCA) and Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III (ACE III)
3. To examine the effect of gender on character human strengths.
4. To study the effect of gender on cognitive impairment (using both measures H-MoCA and ACE III).
5. To explore the relationship between character human strengths and cognitive impairment (using both measures H-MoCA and ACE III).

Review of Literature

By the end of 2022, approximately, 800 studies were administered on character strengths (VIA Institute, 2023), divided into two main categories: improving mental health and well-being (Niemi, 2023). Studies report that successful aging and subjective well being are both positively correlated with spirituality, love and zest among adults and youths (Ardelt et al., 2013; Neto et al., 2014; Toner et al., 2012; McGrath, 2015; Park et al., 2006) whereas Noronha et al., (2016) reported that creativity, perspective, love, teamwork, prudence, and gratitude were each significantly correlated with subjective well being. Strengths such as hope, zest, love, curiosity, gratitude and perseverance, humour, vitality and social intelligence were positively correlated with life satisfaction whereas modesty, prudence, fairness and religiosity appreciation of beauty, creativity, judgment and love of learning were negatively correlated (Ruch et al; 2010; Noronha et al., 2016). Character strengths play a dominant role on emotional coping. Further, the strength of love was found to be prominent for physical, social and mental health. Also, strengths such as

perspective, kindness, hope, humor and curiosity have a general effect on mental health. Character strengths such as perseverance and self-regulation showed specific effect on physical health, spirituality and social intelligence have effects on social health and creativity impacts mental health (Niemic, 2023).

Studies report that demented people naturally exhibit love, kindness and humor to people living with dementia, a neuro-cognitive disorder categorized under DSM 5 (McGee et al., 2023 Hickman et al., (2018). Recent research in the U.S. revealed that the prevalence of cognitive decline among individuals aged 45-64 was nearly 11% (Directors NC for CD 2018). India is experiencing the same phenomenon. A study across six low and middle-income countries (LMICs) including India found that nearly one-sixth of older adults suffer from cognitive decline (Smith et al., 2022). A factsheet of WHO (2017) between 2015 and 2050, the proportion of the world's population over 60 years will nearly double, from 12% to 22%.

Retirement is often associated with greater declines in cognitive functioning, even after controlling for age, health, and socioeconomic status (Bamia et al., 2008; Moon et al., 2012; Fonseca et al., 2017 & Meng et al., 2017, Strickhouser et al, 2021). However, this risk of cognitive impairment associated with retirement is partly inhibited among retirees who regularly engage in mentally stimulating hobbies (Lee et al., 2019) and who maintain a strong social network (Börsch-Supan et al., 2013). Baumann et al., (2020) report that being retired is associated with lower scores in most strength, except modesty and prudence that were higher in retired people. The relationships of several strengths, namely curiosity, kindness, teamwork, modesty, prudence, self-regulation, appreciation of beauty and excellence, and gratitude was stronger in the retired group than in the employed group. Jahoda's (1981) **latent deprivation model** includes five positive factors inherent in employment: time structure, purpose, social interaction, status, and activity which enhance positive mental health and is the outcome of blend of character strengths and virtues (Kumar et al. 2020). Husain (2021) found that women had significantly higher levels of wisdom, justice, curiosity, love of learning, social intelligence, leadership and appreciation of beauty and excellence and women are more virtuous than men. Another comprehensive meta-analysis suggests that females scored higher in appreciation of beauty and excellence, kindness, love, and gratitude. However, the differences were generally small, indicating that males and females are largely similar in their character strengths (Heintz et al., 2017). Rajhans (2015) reported no significant gender differences across these variables. Women generally exhibit higher prevalence rates of cognitive impairment compared to men. In a Shanghai study, 18.9% of women aged 60 and above had MCI, compared to 10.2% of men. (Liu et al., 2022, Oliver et al., 2022, Saha et al, 2024).

Methodology

Research design: The present work is non-experimental ex-post facto study in which both the IVs (activity status and gender) were of selection variables types. A between-group design used to compare the mean of different gender and activity statuses of the participants. Further, correlation sought between character human strengths and cognitive impairment.

Tools Used

VIA-72 is derived by Dr. Robert McGrath from the original VIA-IS by extracting 3 most internally consistent items from each scale. Internal consistency reliability is .75 on average and initial validity coefficient range from .36 to .48. The Hindi version of the tool was provided by VIA INSTITUTE ON CHARACTER. Each character strength is measured by 3 items that are rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (very much unlike me) to 5 (very much like me).

Montreal Cognitive Assessment (H-MoCA)

Montreal Cognitive Assessment is a screening tool to detect mild cognitive impairment, originally developed in 1996 by Ziad Nasreddine in Montreal, Quebec. The Hindi version of Montreal cognitive assessment (H-MoCA) developed by Mansi Gupta et al. (2019) is a one-page 30-point test, takes about 10 minutes to administer. Qualitative review and Content validation ratio (Lawshe) validate the content of H-MoCA with CVR of 0.99. The scale has good internal consistency, (Cronbach's alpha (α) = 0.64) and high test-retest reliability, intra class correlation coefficient, (ICC = 0.87). It is a measure of 7 major cognitive domains namely Visuo-constructional Skills, Naming, Attention, Language, Obstructions, Delayed Recall and Orientation. MoCA scores range between 0 and 30. A score of 26 or over is considered to be normal.

Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination (ACE III)

The ACE-III is a simple, brief, paper-and-pencil-based measure of global cognitive functions. It measures five specific cognitive ability namely, attention and orientation, memory, verbal fluency, language and visuo-spatial abilities, contributing to the overall score of 100 points. A higher score is interpreted as better cognitive ability. The test is available in many languages, including Tamil, Hindi, Indian English, Kannada, Telugu, Malay, Urdu, and Marathi. The optimal cut-off values to detect MCI with ACE-III is 71 (Sensitivity: 77.93; Speficity: 78.42; AUC (95% CI: 0.849).

The present study has measured Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) using two measures namely, Montreal Cognitive Assessment (H-MoCA) and Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III (ACE III). Although, both measure MCI, however, they have their own salient features and advantages. Both H-MoCA and ACE III measure the visuo-spatial cognitive function but ACE III also measures executive functions that is not measured by H-MoCA. Further, ACE III also differentiates between dementia and non-dementia but H-MoCA has an advantage to screen out MCI at an early stage. In essence, both measure MCI but in a way they also complement each other and provide a comprehensive picture of deterioration in cognitive functioning. That's why we decided to use both tools in our study to get a comprehensive picture of cognitive impairment among aged people.

Sampling

Sample: Sample consisted of 100 individuals (51 male and 49 females), age ranged between 60-83 years, Mean Age= 68.09 (male M= 69.13, female M= 67.0). Out of these 100 participants, 26 were still practicing their profession, 68 were retired but living an active life and 6 were those who were retired and leading an inactive life. All the participants belonged to North-Eastern Uttar Pradesh and are living with their families. Purposive Sampling was utilized for the selection of sample.

Inclusion Criteria: Individuals with normal aging process or undergoing only age specific deterioration were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals undergoing treatment of any kind of dementia or dementia due to any other medical condition excluded. Those who were unable to complete the assessment also excluded.

Result and Discussion

To know the effect of activity status, gender on Character human strengths and cognitive impairment 6 One-Way Analysis of Variance calculated. To measure cognitive impairment two standardized test were utilized by the researcher. One is Montreal Cognitive Assessment (H-MoCA) having 7 dimensions, namely Visuo-constructional Skills, Naming, Attention, Language, Obstructions, Delayed Recall, Orientation with its total score. Another is, Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III (ACE III) having 5 dimensions, namely Attention, Memory, Fluency, Language and Visuo-spatial Abilities, with its total

score. Another was. For Character human strengths, score of 6 Virtues along with its total taken for analysis.

Table 1 shows that the main effect of activity status was found to be significant on Character human strengths [$F(2,97) = 6.35, p < 0.001$], scores of H-MoCA [$F(2,97) = 3.84, p < 0.01$] and scores of ACE III [$F(2,97) = 3.88, p < 0.01$]. The respective means suggest that group of practicing professional has scored more in comparison to the retired and active group and retired and inactive Group and are more virtuous and manifest higher level of character human strengths. Further, for the scores of H-MoCA and ACE III it is evident that practicing professionals have manifested higher scores on dimensions of cognitive impairment measures whereas retired and active persons and retired and inactive individuals have manifested impairment.

Table 1

Summary Table of Mean, Standard Deviation and F Value of Character Human Strengths and Cognitive Impairment as a Function of Activity Status of Aged People

Measure	Practicing Professionals		Retired and Active		Retired and Inactive		F
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
Character Human Strengths	102.18	9.20	93.19	13.31	86.66	14.52	6.35**
Cognitive Impairment							
H-MoCA	23.15	4.51	20.94	5.01	17.66	3.07	3.84**
ACE III	69.46	9.67	64.70	10.18	58.33	6.12	3.88**

Note: H-MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment; ACE III: Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III

** $p < 0.01$

Moreover, the main effect of activity status was found to be significant for the virtue of wisdom and knowledge [$F(2, 97) = 8.372, p < 0.01$], for the virtue of humanity [$F(2, 97) = 5.06, p < 0.01$], for the virtue of justice [$F(2, 97) = 7.53, p < 0.01$] and for the virtue of transcendence [$F(2, 97) = 5.33, p < 0.01$]. Further, the mean suggested that the aged individuals who are still practicing their profession exhibit higher wisdom and knowledge ($M = 21.21$), humanity ($M = 16.93$), justice ($M = 13.17$) and transcendence ($M = 21.06$) in comparison to those who are retired and active (wisdom and knowledge ($M = 18.31$), humanity ($M = 12.13$), justice ($M = 11.77$) and transcendence ($M = 19.51$)) as well as retired and inactive [wisdom and knowledge ($M = 17.65$), humanity ($M = 11.21$), justice ($M = 10.66$) and transcendence ($M = 17.81$)].

Table 2

Summary Table of Mean, Standard Deviation and F Value of Cognitive Impairment (H-MoCA) as a Function of Gender of Aged People

Measure	Male		Female		F
	M	SD	M	SD	
Character Human Strengths	96.95	11.51	93.24	14.50	2.02
Cognitive Impairment					
H-MoCA	22.56	4.29	20.02	5.26	7.05**
ACE III	67.70	9.31	63.32	10.63	4.81**

Note: H-MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment; ACE III: Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III

** $p < 0.01$

Table 2 shows that the main effect of gender was not found significant for all the Virtues and Character human strengths. However, the difference was found to be significant for both the measures of cognitive impairment, H-MoCA [$F(1,98) = 7.05, p < 0.01$] and ACE III [$F(1,98) = 4.81, p < 0.01$] which signifies that there is a significant difference between the means of males and females on both measures of cognitive impairment (H-MoCA and ACE III).

Table 3
Descriptive Tables and Correlation of Virtues and Character Human Strengths (Total) with H-MoCA (Total) and ACE III (Total)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Wisdom and Knowledge	-								
2 Courage	.74**	-							
3 Humanity	.75**	.84**	-						
4 Justice	.78**	.70**	.83**	-					
5 Temperance	.78**	.63**	.70**	.73**	-				
6 Transcendence	.82**	.82**	.87**	.78**	.79**	-			
7 CHS (Total)	.88**	.88**	.91**	.88**	.86**	.93**	-		
8 H-MoCA (Total)	.41**	.51**	.38**	.34**	.40**	.54**	.48**	-	
9 ACE III (Total)	.47**	.46**	.37**	.41**	.44**	.54**	.51**	.84**	-

Note: CHS: Character Human Strengths; H-MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment;
ACE III: Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III

** $p < 0.01$

One of the major objectives of the present study was to explore the relationship of Character human strengths and cognitive impairment among the aged people. Total score of Character human strengths and H-MoCA was correlated ($r = .48$, $p < 0.01$). Total score of Character human strengths and ACE-III was found to be correlated ($r = .51$, $p < 0.01$). Various virtues were found to be significantly correlated with both the measures of cognitive impairment (Correlation ranged from .34 to .54). Total scores of H-MoCA and ACE-III was found to be highly correlated ($r = .84$, $p < 0.01$). (Table no. 3).

Discussion

As our first hypothesis stated that different samples of activity status would score variedly on Character human strengths supported by our data and findings revealed that the group having more activity scored higher on character human strengths. Very few studies have been conducted to tap this relationship but they usually consider the pre and post- retirement group of people (Baumann et al., 2020). But in our study we tried to see the relationship between varied activity statuses with character human strengths irrespective of their employment status. The result from the present study supported our second hypothesis that participants having varied activity status would perform with variability on both the measures of cognitive impairment (MoCA and ACE III). Most of the studies conducted in this line, have involved the post-retirement group of people (Bamia et al., 2008; Moon et al., 2012; Fonseca et al., 2017 & Meng et al., 2017, Strickhouser et al, 2021). However, in our study we observed the difference of cognitive impairment among aged who are either practicing their profession or regularly engage themselves mentally, physically or socially or are leading an inactive life. Our results revealed that activity is associated with inhibition in cognitive impairment. Similar findings have been reported in studies conducted by Lee et al (2019) and Börsch-Supan et al (2013).

A probable explanation for the above findings is that the working life not only involves schedules, constraints but also provides to individuals a great source of social support and a sense of self-efficacy. A great amount of cognitive resources is required to maintain both professional and daily life activities. Leaving the workplace is therefore a major life event that implies that the individuals have to leave an environment in which he/she is involved for a very long period. Therefore, the transition phase of retirement is assumed to cause a decline in cognitive functioning

Further, the third hypothesis of our study, that male and female would produce varied outcomes on character human strengths was rejected as our finding suggested that both male and female have responded in the same manner on virtues and character human

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strengths. Our finding is supported by the studies done by Heintz et al., (2017) and Rajhans (2015). Contradictory findings have been reported in previous study conducted by Husain (2021).

From the obtained results, it is evident males have gained higher scores on dimensions of cognitive impairment measures in comparison to females which means males have lower cognitive impairment in comparison to females, supporting the fourth hypothesis of the present study. Similar findings were reported by (Liu et al., 2022, Oliver et al., 2022, Saha et al, 2024).

In line with the third objective, it was hypothesized that character human strengths would be correlated with both the measures of cognitive impairment (H-MoCA and ACE III). The results illustrated that all 6 Virtues and Character Human Strengths (Total) have correlated positively with scores of H-MoCA (Total) and ACE III (Total) which means that higher values on strengths and virtues yielded higher values on H-MoCA and ACE III. It implies that more virtuous individuals would manifest lower cognitive impairment.

Conclusion

Aging and retirement present challenges to cognitive health, but character human strengths and active lifestyles can offer resilience against cognitive impairment. By fostering positive traits and engaging in regular activities, aged individuals can enhance their cognitive reserve, promote character human strengths and virtues, facilitate their cognitive health and inhibit cognitive impairment.

Suggestions for the future Study Future studies should be designed to evaluate the association of character human strengths and cognitive impairment with various other constructs namely, affectivity, meta-memory, and memory self-efficacy. Further, a longitudinal study is suggested for investigating the impact of modification in lifestyle activities on character human strengths and cognitive impairment. There is a need to develop an intervention module to encourage aged individuals to cultivate character strengths in order to support their cognitive health. Moreover, there are very few studies that support our line of reasoning; therefore there is a need to do more replications of the present study to reach on a convincing conclusion.

Limitation of the Study Although the current study found a number of interesting and noble results, it is important to qualify these findings with a discussion of study's limitations.

1. Participants of this study were selected only from Gorakhpur and Maharajganj district of Uttar Pradesh and few samples from the state capital, Lucknow. Also the sample size was not large. Inclusion of the participants from other districts of state might have further strengthened, and could be generalized on the larger population.
2. Purposive sampling was done which may place restrictions on the generalization of the results.
3. In addition, the study used self- reported questionnaire for collecting data. It would be useful to get information from other sources, such as qualitative interviews or observation techniques.

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